

**Reproductive biology of *Turbo sarmaticus*
at Dwesa-Cwebe Nature Reserve**

By

Inam Yekwayo

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Department of Zoology,
Walter Sisulu University**

Supervisor: Dr M. D. V. Nakin

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ABSTRACT

The reproductive biology of giant periwinkle (*Turbo sarmaticus*) was investigated using gravimetric method. Samples were randomly collected from Dwesa-Cwebe Nature Reserve during spring low tide from June 1996 to July 1997 and preserved in 10% formalin seawater. A 2-way Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) test was used to test the effect of gender and month on the Gonado-Somatic Index (GSI) using the operculum diameter as covariate. The results indicated that the male GSI was greater than the female GSI and this was due to the selective predation. The results showed synchronized spawning period of both males and females. Results from Chi-squared tests showed a distortion from a 1:1 sex ratio with significantly more males than females. Males appeared to attain size at sexual maturity earlier than females. Spawning of *T. sarmaticus* occurred in warmer months and temperature was found to be the important factor triggering spawning. Information obtained from this study may possibly add value on the effective management of this species.

Key words: *Turbo sarmaticus*, reproductive cycle, spawning period, sex ratio, sexual maturity.

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INTRODUCTION

Turbo sarmaticus (the giant periwinkle) has a world wide distribution and is also found in the shores of South Africa where the distribution ranges from False Bay to the former Transkei (Foster *et al.* 2000). It inhabits both the intertidal and sub tidal zones, but it is primarily restricted to hard substrates. It is the largest of the four endemic *Turbo* species commonly found in South Africa and inhabits the lower littoral and shallow sub littoral regions to a depth of approximately 8 m (Yssel 1989; Bruton *et al.* 1991; Branch *et al.* 2002). It lives in the submerged reefs and boulders in South African seashore. *T. sarmaticus* populations are regionally sustainable and persisted along the southeast coast due to the adjacent intertidal and sub tidal refuge populations (Proudfoot 2007).

The giant periwinkle is a large sea snail which is round, slow-growing marine gastropod and belongs to the family Turbanidae. Turbanidae have *Turbo* species that are almost spherical or top shaped, smooth or strongly ornamented, some have spines or flutings with pearly aperture, and most of them occur in warm waters around coral reefs including *Turbo marmoratus*, *T. petholotus* and *T. sarmaticus* (Vermeij *et al.* 2007). Branch (2002) suggested that the Turbinidae tends to be the most conspicuous and abundant in temperate and tropical waters.

T. sarmaticus has shells that have a round smooth aperture and solid dome-shaped hard calcareous operculum, which is thick, white, and densely covered in knobles. The operculum is calcified to function as the passive defensive structures against predators that break the shell at the lip or enter the shell by the way of aperture (Vermeij *et al.*

2007) and it is also characterized by having three rows of low nodules spiral around each whorl. It is also characterized by the colour of the inner lip which ranges from white to bright orange and outer lip has dark brown or black (Branch *et al.* 2002).

The species is harvested for food as it has a tasty flesh and is the preferred food item for many poor rural communities. *T. sarmaticus* is susceptible to over-exploitation due to it being a sedentary animal, inhabiting easily accessible zones on the shore. In the Eastern Cape coast of South Africa, it is one of the most heavily exploited target organism. This is due to the increase in population growth and poverty, so people usually feed on them (McLachlan *et al.* 1981). *T. sarmaticus* has no commercial value; it is harvested by subsistence fishers for food and by recreational sector for bait (Yssel 1989). According to the Marine Living Resource Act of 1998, this species has a bag limit of five individuals per person, per day with a minimum size limit of 63.5mm. However, due to the lack of law enforcement the large individual species are becoming increasingly scarce and are threatened of becoming extinct. *T. sarmaticus* shell has silvery white mother-of-pearl deposits combined with its natural rusty brown colour that make the outer shell patterns fascinating and perfect material for jewelry items and this shell is also used for making Shiva pendants, Shiva rings and Shiva earrings (Vermeij *et al.* 2007).

T. sarmaticus is the prominent macro algal grazers feeding on various forms of algae, which include Rhodophyta, Chlorophyta and Phaeophyta (Foster *et al.* 1998). They are dioecious broadcast spawners where they release their gametes into the water with fertilization occurring by chance. These slow-growing gastropods reach a size of about 6

cm after three to four years and have the maximum size that grows to approximately 3 inches (76 mm) and their maximum shell length is 120 mm (Proudfoot *et al.* 2006).

There are many factors affecting reproduction of marine gastropods and they include environmental factors (temperature), nutrient availability and the tides (Lasiak 1986; Foster *et al.* 1999). Henninger *et al.* (2001) noted that the reproductive biology can be influenced by phases of the moon, photoperiod and mechanical stimulation. The rough seas and oceanic down welling triggers spawning (Ward *et al.* 2002).

Many studies have been done on *Turbo sarmaticus* in South Africa and these include: growth and production (McLachlan & Lombard 1981), consumption and digestibility of macro algae (Foster & Hodgson 1998), growth rate and reproductive fitness (Foster *et al.* 1999), population structure (Foster *et al.* 2000), exploitation status (Proudfoot *et al.* 2006) and population structure, growth and recruitment (Proudfoot 2007). Relating to other regions of South Africa, there are few studies done in the former Transkei on *T. sarmaticus*. Thus, the aim of this study was to investigate the reproductive biology of the *T. sarmaticus*, focusing on the spawning period of males and females, sex ratio and size at sexual maturity. Such information may play an important role in the effective management of this species.

METHODS AND MATERIALS

This study was laboratory based with samples that were already collected randomly from Dwesa-Cweba Nature Reserve (32°18'S, 28°50'E) over a period of 13 months, from June 1996 to July 1997 and preserved in 10% formalin sea water. Dwesa-Cweba Nature Reserve is situated in the central wild coast and is bordered on one side by the Indian Ocean and on the other side by rugged grassland of the former Transkei. It is found in the southern region of Transkei lying between Nqabara and Mbashe rivers (Fig. 1). It is covered by lowland forest but also support grassland and acacia scrub.

The reproductive biology of the *Turbo sarmaticus* species was studied for a period of 13 months. About 30 specimens with varying sizes were randomly collected, in each month. The shells of the specimens were crushed with great care not to damage the tissues using the hammer to expose the animal. After the removal of the shell, the specimen were dissected out to separate gonads from the body tissues and sexed by visual observation. The female gonads were identified by green colour and males by white colour. The diameter of the operculum was measured to the nearest 0.05mm using Veiner calipers. The spawning period of *T. sarmaticus* was determined using gravimetric method, which is the measurement method, based on weighing samples.

Gravimetric method

Gravimetric method has been used successfully to determine reproductive cycle by many authors in *Turbo* species (Foster *et al.* 1999; Ward *et al.* 2002). Dry gonads and dry body tissues including the operculum were weighed to the nearest 0.01g after oven drying to a constant weight at 60°C for a period of 48 hours. The mean monthly Gonado-Somatic Index (GSI) of both males and females for each month was calculated. The GSI was expressed as a percentage of gonad weight divided by the body weight including the operculum but excluding the shell using the formula:

$$\text{GSI} = \frac{\text{Dry gonad weight}}{\text{Dry body weight (including operculum)}} \times 100$$

An increase in the GSI indicated the gonadal development and the decrease in GSI indicated spawning period.

Size at sexual maturity

Size at sexual maturity was determined based on the size frequency looking at 50% of smallest animals with mature gonads.

Statistical analysis

A two-way Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was used to test the effect of gender and month on the GSI of *T. sarmaticus* and the operculum was used as the covariate. Prior to the use ANCOVA, the data were tested for normality and homogeneity of variance using Kolmogorov Smirnov test and Cochran test, respectively (Zar 1996 and Underwood 1997).

Post-hoc tests were used following significant results from ANCOVA tests. A Chi-square test was used to test for any deviation from 1:1 sex ratio of *T. sarmaticus*.

Fig. 1: Map showing the location of the study site along the Transkei coast.

RESULTS

The results showed significant differences ($p < 0.05$) in month, sex and the covariate (operculum diameter) on \pm GSI of *T. sarmaticus* (Table 1). There were no significant differences ($p > 0.05$) on the interaction of month (Table 1). The monthly mean GSI showed two peaks, a major peak and a minor peak occurring in September 1996 and May 1997, respectively (Fig. 1.1.) The mean GSI of males were significantly greater than that of females (Fig. 1.2.).

Month effect

There was an increase in the mean GSI of *T. sarmaticus* from August 1996 to September 1996 and from March to May 1997. This increase in mean GSI, reached the highest peak in September for the major peak and May for the minor peak. This suggests an increase in the gonadal development during these periods. There was a decrease in the mean GSI from September 1996 to December 1996 and from May 1997 to June 1997 and that decrease indicated occurrence of spawning. The lowest and highest mean value of GSI were 6.693 ± 0.495 and 17.669 ± 0.508 reached in August and September, respectively (Fig. 1.1.). Post-hoc tests showed significant differences ($p < 0.05$) in months showing the peaks (Table 2).

Sex effect

There were significant differences on the sexes ($p < 0.05$) on mean GSI of *T. sarmaticus* (Table 1). The male GSI was greater than the female GSI; it was 12.791 for males and 11.791 for females.

The GSI of males was slightly greater than that of females since the male GSI value males was about 13% and about 11% for females (Fig.1.1).

Sex ratio

The total number of individuals used was 240 and there were 93 females and 147 males. This reflected a male to female sex ratio of 1.58: 1 (i.e. 2: 1). The Chi-square test (X^2) revealed that males were significantly more than females ($X^2 = 0.000491$, $df = 1$, $p < 0.05$).

Size at sexual maturity

The size at sexual maturity showed differences that males matured earlier than females. This reflected that the operculum diameter of matured male and female of 15 mm and 20 mm (Fig. 1.3).

Size frequency distribution

There were no significant differences in the size frequency distribution between males and females (Fig.1.3).The smallest size frequency was 15 mm for male and 20 mm for female *T. sarmaticus*. The biggest size of male and female *T. sarmaticus* observed was 35 mm.

Table 1. A 2-way ANCOVA based on GSI estimates of *Turbo sarmaticus*. *

denotes significant difference at $p < 0.05$.

Source of variation	SS	df	MS	F	p
Operculum (covariate)	704.424	1	704.424	95.5332	< 0.0001*
Month	1689.613	12	140.801	32.0041	< 0.0001*
Sex	99.593	1	99.593	19.46	< 0.000133*
Month*Sex	52.473	12	4.373	0.593	0.846639
Error	1563.205	212	7.374		

Fig.1.1. Overall monthly mean (\pm SE) GSI of *T. sarmaticus*

Table 2. Post hoc tests (Tukeys Honesty Significant Difference) showing homogenous groups among months in *T. sarmaticus*. The symbols *** in the same class indicate no significant differences.

Month	GSI	Homogenous groups						
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Aug' 96	8.2691	***						
Jun' 96	8.4946	***	***					
Dec' 96	9.4772	***	***	***				
Mar' 97	10.6211	***	***	***	***			
Jan' 97	10.7958	***	***	***	***		***	
Jul' 96	11.2649		***	***	***		***	
Jun' 97	12.3307			***	***	***	***	
Feb' 97	12.3926			***	***	***	***	
Apr' 97	13.4367				***	***	***	***
Nov' 96	14.0703					***		***
Oct' 96	14.4606					***	***	***
May' 97	15.2011							***
Sep' 96	15.9185							***

Fig.1.2. Overall mean (+SE) GSI of male and female *T.sarmaticus*. Letters above the bar columns represents homogenous groups.

Fig.1.3. Size frequency distribution (operculum diameter) of male and female *Turbo sarmaticus* at Dwesa-Cwebe Nature Reserve.

DISCUSSION

This project indicated two spawning events of *Turbo sarmaticus* the major one occurred from September to March (spring to summer) and the minor one from May to June (autumn to winter). This trend maybe attributed to increased seawater temperature. Joll (1980) stated that increased water temperature induce spawning of *T. intercostalis* and *T. torquatus*. *T. intercostalis* and *T. torquatus* have a continuous gametogenesis and prolonged breeding seasons, whereby *T. torquatus* showed several spawning per year with the peak of activity in summer whilst *T. intercostalis* spawns from autumn to spring but an exceptional once occurred whereby spawning occurred in summer. Lasiak (1986) noted that the spawning of the *T. coronatus* coincides with the increase in sea temperature whereby the peak in spawning occurred during the period of maximum sea temperature. In contrast to these findings, Ward *et al.* (2002) noted that the water temperature play no role in inducing spawning of *T. torquatus*.

Another factor known to trigger spawning was found to be the nutrient availability (Foster *et al.* 1999). They reported that along the southeastern coast of South Africa, *T. sarmaticus* had a distinct reproductive cycle with gametogenesis occurring from autumn until spring and spawning occurring in summer and this was because of the increased nutrient availability. Lasiak (1986) suggested that nutrient availability could affect spawning since spawning is dependant on the completion of vitellogenesis, which is also dependent on the nutrient availability that is either in the form of nutrient reserve or food ingested. Foster *et al.* (1999) showed that reproductive fitness of marine species was dramatically influenced by the diet whereby when the animals are placed under nutritive

stress, the reproductive output decreases. The reproductive cycle of many marine invertebrates is known to be energetically demanding and relies on the utilization of accumulated stored glycogen reserves for egg development since the low glycogen levels lead to the decrease in the reproductive fitness (Foster *et al.* 1999)

Tides were reported to affect the reproduction of marine species since at low tides they do not feed; therefore, they cannot reproduce properly (Lasiak 1986). Ward *et al.* (2002) noted that the rough seas and oceanic down welling triggers spawning in archeogastropods, this may ensure that the eggs and the larvae have a good chance of successful fertilization and dispersal from their natal reef.

The results from this study showed that male and female reproduction was highly synchronized. The results of this study are similar to those found by Ward *et al.* (2002) who suggested that male and female *Turbo torquatus* within a population underwent synchronous gonad development and spawning whereby two spawning events occurred each year with a spawning event occurring from autumn-winter and another from spring-summer and these events were asynchronous. The results showed that *T. sarmaticus* is a partially spawner because gonads were never completely spent and this is similar to the results found by (Ward *et al.* 2002) for *Turbo torquatus*.

Hinninger *et al.* (2002) noted that spawning synchrony could be correlated to factors such as temperature, phases of the moon, photoperiod, food abundance and mechanical stimulation.

Ward *et al.* (2002) found that *T. torquatus* is capable of incomplete spawning. Lasiak (1986) stated that *Turbo coronatus* has a protracted breeding period with peak spawning taking place from December to February and observed gametogenic progression between August and December.

This study showed that the male *T. sarmaticus* had a greater GSI than the female *T. sarmaticus*. Similarly, Foster *et al.* (1999) noted that the males had a greater Gonado-Somatic Index than females from both populations and GSI on south west coast were greater than southeast coast. The results indicated that during spawning of *T. sarmaticus* there was a decrease in the GSI. Joll (1980) noted that during spawning in *T. intercostalis*, there was an increase in the number of immature oocytes, which indicates the high rate of oocyte production and there was a decrease in the mean percentage of mature oocytes.

This project showed that, the sex ratio of *T. sarmaticus* was significantly different between the sexes with more males than females. This distortion in sex ratio may be due to the selective predation. In contrast, Ward *et al.* (2002) found more females than males in older populations of dioecious molluscs. However, Joll (1980) found that *T. intercostalis* and *T. torquatus* are dioecous with 1:1 sex ratio.

There results indicated that male *T. sarmaticus* appeared to attained size at sexual maturity earlier than the females. Although there were no significant differences in size frequency distribution between sexes, this effect suggest further investigation.

In conclusion *T. sarmaticus* was found to be a partially spawner since the gonads were never completely spent. Two spawning events were noted to occur from September to December 1996 and from May to June 1997 and suggested that temperature plays an important role in triggering spawning of *T. sarmaticus*. It can be recommended the same project be repeated but in a different area since things change in space and time and also the use of histological analysis to compare the results.

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